

Theoretical underpinnings

Theoretical Foundations	Conceptual Elements		Definition	Reference	
Cryptoeconomics	Blockchain	Public	Does not require approval or authorization for access	(LAI; CHUEN, 2018), (XU et al., 2017), (BAMBARA; ALLEN, 2018)	
		Private	Requires authentication of participant identities and authorization of participant's permission-level of access		
		Consortium	The consensus is controlled by preauthorized nodes, being public or restricted the right to read		
		Mechanism Design		The science of designing rules of a game to achieve a specific outcome, even though each participant may be self-interested	(PHELPS et al., 2010)
	Token Offering	Exchange	Synonymous with crypto currencies, functioning as a decentralized tool to enable the buying and selling of goods and services	(CLAYTON, 2017), (LUX; MATHYS, 2018), (BRADDICK et al., 2018), (LUX; MATHYS, 2018), (BRADDICK et al., 2018), (CARRIÈRE, 2019), (BASEL, 2019), (BLANDIN et al., 2019), (COINMARKETCAP, 2021), (ETHERSCAN, 2021), (STOSCOPE, 2021)	
		Security	Represents tangible or intangible assets such as participations in real physical underlying's		
		Utility	Can be redeemed by investors for access to a specific product or service once developed		
	Governance		Means of achieving the direction, control, and coordination of stakeholders within the context of a given blockchain project to which they jointly contribute	(LUX; MATHYS, 2018)	
Business Model Innovation	Business Model Design		Entrepreneurial activity of creating, developing and validating a BM for a newly formed organization	(MASSA; TUCCI, 2013)	
	Business Model Reconfiguration		Phenomena by which managers reconfigure organizational resources to change a BM		
	Value Proposition	Value Creation	Means to create a business value from the needs of the customer which comes from the desire to use the value	(BASEL, 2019) (AMIT; ZOTT, 2012), (TEECE, 2010), (CHAMBERS; PATROCÍNIO, 2012), (BOWEN et al., 2009)	
		Value Delivery	The architecture of revenue costs and profit associated with the business enterprise delivering that value		
		Value Capture	The realization of exchange value, being determined by the bargaining relationships between buyers and sellers		
	Business Model Elements	Technology	Usage and knowledge of tools, techniques, systems, methods of organizations or material products	(MASON; SPRING, 2011) (KREMER, 1993) (NORMANN, 2001) (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)	
		Market Offering	Not a physical product, but a way to reconfigure activities and stimulate and enable value creation		
Network Architecture		Network of actors that goes beyond a firm's immediate value chain, sometimes including noncommercial players			
Market Shaping	Fan Framework	Business Definition	The lens or frame through which the firm sees the rest of the layers and so is crucial	(NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a), (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018b)	
		Exchange Layer	What product or service is offered, including the pricing logic		
		Network Layer	A network of actors, each with their own roles and know-how and with established relationships between them		
		Representation Layer	Arrangements of coherent but simplified illustrations of what a market is and how it works.		
		Rules Layer	The actions of the players in the market ecosystem are guided by formal and social norms		
		Designable Elements		Parts and agents that can be managed or shaped by a firm	(NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)
	Market Practices	Exchange	Concrete activities related to the consummation of individual economic exchanges	(KJELLBERG; HELGESSON, 2006), (KJELLBERG; HELGESSON, 2007b)	
		Representation	Activities that contribute to depict markets and/or how they work		
		Normalizing	Activities that contribute to establish guidelines for how a market should be (re)shaped or work according to some actor(s).		
		Process of Translation		Denotes a basic social process by which something (such as a token, rule, product, technique, truth, or idea) spreads across time and space	(KJELLBERG; HELGESSON, 2007b) (LATOUR et al., 1999)
	Level of Influence	Technology Level	Functional base for the shaping of single and composite activities, and the creation of useful market offers	(KINDSTRÖM et al., 2018), (ULKUNIEMI et al., 2015), (EDVARDSSON et al., 2014)	
		Market Offer Level	How buyers and sellers organize market activities that facilitate interactions centered on the exchange object		
		System Level	The level at which norms and regulations set the boundaries and rules for an entire market		
		Market Structure		A set of institutions and actors located in a physical or virtual space where market-related transactions and activities take place	(VENKATESH et al., 2006), (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.